

Performance Appraisal for Private Employees: A Study

Sourav Basu

Research scholar, Department of Management, RKDF University, Ranchi, Jharkhand

Dr.Somnath Roy Choudhury

Assistant Professor, Department of Management, RKDF University, Ranchi, Jharkhand

Abstract: A performance review compares actual performance to expected performance. Reviewing numerous performance-influencing variables also helps. The degree of success that individual workers have in achieving this particular objective is crucial in assessing organizational performance since the organization exists to fulfil the goals. Evaluation of an employee's performance in achieving their personal goals is a crucial component of human resource management. This introduces the idea of performance evaluation. In order to better understand the goals of performance assessment implementation, the method of performance appraisal, and the advantages of performance appraisal, the current research was conducted. The researcher has used all secondary sources of data for this goal. A range of books, magazines, and internet sources were consulted in order to get the essential data. The research may be concluded with the finding that performance reviews improve cooperation and boost human resource productivity in the workplace.

Keywords: Performance Assessment, Organization, Employee, Evaluation, Compensation Increases.

INTRODUCTION: Performance review is also known as employee rating, employee assessment, or merit rating. It's a thorough process that compares an employee's current and past work to predetermined goals. It is important to consider both the individual's actual output and the organization's goals when evaluating performance. The idea that a formal evaluation may improve a worker's performance has been around since before humans even started walking upright. When someone learns how they truly did and accepts responsibility for their mistakes, they get motivation.

Almost all businesses have some kind of system in place for rating their personnel. One of the oldest, most common, and ubiquitous management practises is performance appraisal. "To determine an employee's conduct that is linked to performance and integrates with organizational performance is the fundamental goal of performance appraisal. It benefits both employers and workers to comprehend their responsibilities inside the company. Performance expectations are integrated into the performance assessment system, which provides complete transparency between the appraiser and appraisee. It serves as a tool for fostering a positive work environment". Building a friendly, supportive work environment that fosters healthy competition and offers stakeholders and workers a feeling of accomplishment is the goal of every management strategy. "The ideal tool for accomplishing the aforementioned goals, whether directly or indirectly, is a performance assessment system. It enhances interpersonal ties between employers and workers inside the company. It represents an assessment of the qualities, attributes, and work output of the

personnel on the job”. The organization’s and the workers' desire to achieve their objective is a constant process.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM: An appraisal is an evaluation of something's worth or quality. In the workplace, a performance evaluation is a formal assessment of an employee's contributions to the company conducted by their superiors or other knowledgeable individuals. When one person is rated as better or worse than others, this is known as a merit rating or performance evaluation. The main goal of this merit rating is to determine a worker's promotion eligibility. However, since its use goes beyond determining eligibility for promotion, performance evaluation is a more complete phrase for similar operations. In addition to promotion, these actions might include training and development, pay raises, transfers, and discharges. Therefore the problem stated in the present study is “**Performance appraisal for private employees: A study**”

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY: Many businesses use evaluation systems to help their employees and the company as a whole perform better. However, this may not be the end goal. It's possible that a lot of frustration might be avoided if people didn't put so much stock on the results of a single PA exam. For instance, a method that is effective for training and growth may not be the most appropriate for determining pay raises. However, a well-planned system may help businesses reach their objectives and boost employee productivity. . The current research is substantial enough for everyone to take note of in this respect.

OBJECTIVES: The present study has been undertaken with the following objectives-

1. To study the objectives of implementing performance appraisal
2. To study the process of performance appraisal
3. To discuss the benefits of performance appraisal

OBJECTIVES OF PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL: In the words of Cummings, “the overall objective of performance appraisal is to improve the efficiency of an enterprise by attempting to mobilize the best possible efforts from individuals employed in it. Such appraisals achieve four objectives including the salary reviews, the development and training of individuals, planning job rotation and assistance promotions.” Major objectives of performance appraisal are summarized below:

- (i) To provide input on hiring, firing, and reassignment processes.
- (ii) To provide the worker feedback on how he or she is doing.
- (iii) To harmonise individual goals with those of the company.
- (iv) Determine where more training or education is needed among staff members.
- Purpose-wise job-swapping is a key part of (v).
- (vi) Facilitate more two-way communication between upper and lower-level management.
- (vii) to provide input on raise determinations.
- (viii) So that workers may receive criticism and suggestions for improvement.
- (ix) Motivate workers towards greater productivity and success.

Evaluation and formulation of human resource (HR) selection, training, and development programmes.

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PROCESS OF PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL: The process of performance appraisal involves several steps and they are delineated as follows:

1. Preparation – All required paperwork must be prepared, agreed-upon duties must be recorded, and performance, accomplishments, incidents, reports, etc. must be recorded. Previous performance assessment records and a current job description must definitely be included. A good assessment form will give the process a nice, natural order. If the organization doesn't have a standard assessment form, one must discover one or obtain and/or modify the form from a standard website. Regardless of the method used, one must verify that it has received the required organizational authorization and be familiar with its operation. It is necessary to organize the documentation in order to represent the order of the evaluation and to record the order in which the things will be covered.

2. Intimation – The appraisee must be informed of a suitable time and location, which must be changed if necessary, as well as the purpose and type of the appraisal. The appraisee must also be given the opportunity to gather information and pertinent performance and achievement records and materials. An agenda of topics to be discussed should be supplied if the assessment form does not provide a logical sequence for the conversation.

3. Venue – To conduct a successful interview, one must choose a location that is appropriate, planned, and accessible. The same guidelines that apply to recruiting interviews should be followed. Hotel lobbies, public lounges, and canteens must all be avoided since privacy is crucial.

4. Layout - No of the subject matter, everyone should feel comfortable and at ease. Take down the walls. The meeting should not take place in the boss's chair, with the other person sitting submissively on the opposite side of the desk; instead, an informal setting, such as a table, should be established.

5. Introduction – The appraisee must be made comfortable; to do this, one must commence with a positive statement, smile, and be warm and nice. The appraisee may be afraid, thus it is the appraiser's duty to provide a relaxed and non-threatening environment. Set the stage by simply explaining what will occur, inviting conversation and as much participation from the appraisee as possible, and making it clear that it is their meeting. It is necessary to validate the timings, particularly the completion time. One should start with a broad overview of how things have been going, if beneficial and appropriate, but one should avoid delving into details.

6. Reviewing and measurement – Reviewing the activities, tasks, goals, and accomplishments one at a time is necessary in order to prevent veering off topic or expressing imprecise or generalized opinions. If the individual has done their homework well, he will have a direction to follow. If a topic that is off-topic is brought up, it should be recorded. He must focus on precise data and strong supporting arguments rather than speculation, anecdotes, or general judgments, particularly on the appraisee. As with interviews, one of the biggest challenges for the appraiser is remaining objective. Facts and figures are the litmus test and offer a solid neutral foundation for the discussion that is free of bias and personal opinions. According to whichever measurement or scoring method is included in the assessment system, a measure of competence should be agreed upon for each item.

7. Agreeing an action plan - It is important to come to an overall strategy with the appraisee that accounts for the work tasks, career goals, departmental and organizational objectives, and the evaluated 10 strengths and weaknesses. The strategy may be broken down into short-, medium-, and long-term components if required, but it's crucial that it be agreed upon and feasible.

8. Agreeing on specific objectives - These particular goals and activities make up the action plan as a whole. These must follow the SMARTER rules: specified, measurable, agreed, realistic, time-bound,

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pleasurable, documented, as with any assigned job or agreed-upon aim. If not, there is no need to worry. The goals may be whatever the person is willing to commit to and that will be to their advantage. Despite the fact that the majority of goals will often be work-related, one should not limit oneself to these while assisting others in their development.

9. Agreeing on necessary support - Anything that will help the appraisee get closer to the standard and agreed-upon job is fair game, “such as coaching, mentoring, shadowing, distance learning, reading, watching videos, attending meetings and workshops, workbooks, manuals, and guides”. The appraisee will not be successful in reaching their goals without this assistance. Additionally, one should think about "whole-person development" training and development that goes beyond job-related abilities. The individual may desire to improve this skill or pastime. This kind of holistic development will help the person's job and boost motivation and loyalty.

10. Inviting any other points or questions – One must make sure to capture any other concerns.

11. Becoming close – “expressing gratitude to the appraisee for their participation at the meeting and their work during the year, and pledging to assist in any manner possible”.

12. Recording main points, agreed actions and follow-up – As soon as feasible following the meeting, send out any required confirmations and submit any necessary documentation with a copy to the appropriate parties (typically human resources and one's immediate supervisor).

BENEFITS OF PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL: “The benefits typically claimed by those who defend or advocate performance appraisal systems include the following”:

- 1. Feedback** is given to workers during performance assessments, “which typically occur at least once a year and often on an interim basis throughout the year”. As a result, mistakes and waste are decreased, productivity is raised, customer quality and service are better, and employee commitment, ownership, and motivation are all boosted.
- 2. Establishing goals:** Performance review sessions may include discussions about establishing personal goals and professional objectives as well as synchronizing personal and organizational aims.
- 3. Career management:** Performance evaluation meetings provide the chance to explore career advancement prospects and highlight areas that need training and development.

4. **Objective evaluation:** Through the use of consistent procedures and standards, performance evaluations are rendered objective. The foundation for awarding and recognizing individual success is therefore made fair, legitimate, and lawful.

5. **Legal defence:** Performance evaluations provide the company legal defence against employee claims alleging discrimination and wrongful termination. A third benefit, especially if it comes from a direct and perhaps ruthless observer, is that the official performance evaluation system reinforces the organization’s hierarchical power structure. It provides the managing manager, who is effectively using a carrot-and-stick management technique, authority over some of the carrots and sticks.

Benefits of Performance Review for the employee

CONCLUSION: Data gathered from performance reviews may be useful in a number of different HR contexts, such as strategic planning, staffing, development, remuneration, communication, employee relations, and evaluation of new hires. The objectives shared by the personnel and the organization should also be considered while evaluating performance. This is crucial because only when the goals of the organization are met can workers grow. As the company's most valuable asset, employees should be given priority. The organization and its people resources may both grow and develop in tandem with shared aims. They improve cooperation and the efficiency of the organization’s human resources.

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